

A New Synthesis of Serine.

By SUSIL KUMAR MITRA.

Serine, α -amino- β -hydroxypropionic acid, has previously been synthesised by Erlenmeyer, jun., (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3789), by Fischer and Leuchs (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3787), and by Leuchs and Geiger (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 2644). The present paper describes another synthesis of serine by following Gabriel's method of synthesis of α -amino-acids.

The sodium salt of diethyl phthalimidomalonate was condensed with chloromethyl ether, the product being methoxymethylphthalimidomalononic ester (I).

Attempts to hydrolyse (I) to serine by heating with hydrochloric acid of varying strength or hydrobromic acid (d 1.8) in a sealed tube resulted in profound decomposition of the molecule, and phthalic acid and ammonium chloride (or bromide) were formed in quantity even at 100° , while no appreciable change was noticed on boiling the ester with 10 or 20 % hydrochloric acid for about 5 hours. The formation of the ammonium salt is probably due to the labile nature of the NH_2 -group, attached to a reactive methylene group. Success was however attained by conducting the experiment with concentrated hydrobromic acid at 48° , when the primary product was found to be methoxymethylphthalimidomalononic acid. On heating above its melting point, this substance yielded an oil which was

converted into serine hydrochloride by heating with fuming hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 100°.

Methoxymethylphthalimidomalonic ester (I) gives considerable quantities of phthalic acid by hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide (N to 5N) between 50° and 100°. By conducting the hydrolysis in alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution, a potassium salt, $C_{13}H_{10}O_8NK_3$, presumably (II), was obtained. The acid was unstable. On treatment with hydrochloric acid, carbon dioxide was evolved and a viscous oil separated out. This oil on being boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave serine hydrochloride.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phthalimidomalonic Ester.—Sorensen's method (*Compt. rend.*, 1903, 6, 1) was modified as follows:

Potassium phthalimide and ethyl bromomalonate were heated for 2 hours under reflux in xylene solution. The filtrate, after separation of potassium bromide, was freed from xylene under reduced pressure, when, pure phthalimidomalonic ester (m. p. 73°) was obtained in an yield of 78 per cent.

Methoxymethylphthalimidomalonic Ester (I).—The interaction of phthalimidomalonic ester (20 g.) and sodium (1.6 g.), in ethereal solution, though at first vigorous, stops after a time owing to the formation of an incrustation of the resulting sodium salt. In presence of a little alcohol, the reaction proceeds smoothly. To the cooled sodium salt, chloromethyl ether (9 g in 20 c.c. ether) was added drop by drop. The reaction was complete in about 2 hours. The mixture was diluted with water, the ethereal layer separated, dried over ignited sodium sulphate and the ether removed, when the substance was left behind as silky needles (yield, 60%). It is soluble in benzene, xylene, ether, acetone and hot alcohol, and sparingly soluble in cold alcohol. It was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m. p. 127°. (Found: C, 58.4; H, 5.4; N, 4.01. $C_{17}H_{19}O_7N$ requires C, 58.45; H, 5.44; N, 4.01 per cent.).

Methoxymethylphthalimidomalonic Acid.—The above ester (10 g.) and hydrobromic acid (50 c. c. d 1.8) were heated in a sealed tube at 49° for 2 hours, when the substance gradually went into solution, and ethyl bromide separated out as an oil. On opening the tube and keeping at 50-60° for some time to remove ethyl

bromide and hydrobromide acid fumes, the above acid separated out along with a little phthalic acid. This was quickly filtered off and the filtrate diluted to twice its volume with water and cooled in ice when the pure acid crystallised out (yield, 50%). It melts at 102°, and dissolves easily in ether and acetone but with difficulty in alcohol. It is sparingly soluble in water (hot or cold) and was separated from phthalic acid by digestion with hot water. On long standing in presence of concentrated acid, it suffered hydrolysis. At 140-145° it evolves carbon dioxide forming an oil. (Found: C, 54.2; H, 4.1; N, 4.65. $C_{13}H_{11}O_7N$ requires C, 53.24; H, 3.75; N, 4.77 per cent.).

The *silver salt* was prepared by adding silver nitrate to the aqueous potassium salt of the acid. The precipitate, a white granular powder, was washed with water and dried in an amber coloured desiccator. (Found: Ag, 32.3, $C_{13}H_9O_7NAg_2$ requires Ag, 42.6 per cent.).

Serine Hydrochloride.—Methoxymethylphthalimidomalonic acid (5 g.) was heated with fuming hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) in a sealed tube on the water-bath for 9 hours. Phthalic acid was filtered off from the reaction products, the solution was extracted with ether and the aqueous portion was concentrated on a water-bath. The syrupy liquid deposits, on standing, crystals of serine hydrochloride (yield, 50%). (Found: C, 24.7; H, 5.9; N, 9.71. $C_3H_7O_3N$, HCl requires C, 25.4; H, 5.65; N, 9.9 per cent.).

Alkaline Hydrolysis of Methoxymethylphthalimidomalonic Ester.—To a saturated hot alcoholic solution of the ester (10 g.) was gradually added a hot saturated solution of potassium hydroxide in alcohol (6 g.). The yellow solution soon became colourless and a white precipitate began to come down. After refluxing for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the precipitate was collected, dissolved in the minimum quantity of water and reprecipitated by alcohol (yield, 80%). (Found: N, 3.33; K, 27.79. $C_{13}H_{10}O_8NK_3$ requires N, 3.29; K, 27.53 per cent.).

The above potassium salt was gradually treated with *N/10*-hydrochloric acid, till the solution was acid to congo-red. Carbon dioxide was profusely evolved and the solution was evaporated down on a water-bath when an oil was left behind. The oil was taken up with alcohol, the alcohol removed and the residual oil heated with four times its weight of fuming hydrochloric acid under reflux for 4 hours. Phthalic acid was then removed from the cooled reaction product, the solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue taken up

with a minimum quantity of water and filtered. The filtrate was again concentrated and allowed to stand when serine hydrochloride separated out (yield, 55%). (Found: C, 25.9; H, 5.7; N, 10.1. $C_3H_7O_3N.HCl$ requires C, 25.4; H, 5.65; N, 9.9 per cent.).

Serine.—Serine hydrochloride (5 g.) solution was vigorously agitated with freshly precipitated moist silver oxide (6 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ minute and quickly filtered. The filtrate was digested with animal charcoal for 1 hour, filtered, the filtrate concentrated on water-bath, and the serine precipitated by alcohol. It was finally crystallised from water (yield, 90%). It shrinks at 208° and melts at 246° (decomp.). (Found: C, 34.5; H, 6.8; N, 13.26. $C_3H_7O_3N$ requires C, 34.28; H, 6.6; N, 13.3 per cent.).

The *phenyl cyanate* derivative melted at 159° (*cf.* Fischer and Leuchs, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 12.32. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{12}O_4N_2$ N, 12.5 per cent.).

In conclusion I wish to express my sincere thanks to Sir P. C. Ray for his kind interest in this investigation and for placing the resources of his research laboratory at my disposal.

SIR T. N. PALIT LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received May 14, 1930.